

The Urbanization of Revolt: The Case of the October 2019 Uprisings in Lebanon

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The recent student encampments in the United States, Europe, and across the Middle East over the conflict in Gaza have renewed interest in understanding student activism and its broader political impacts. This entry examines the October 2019 uprising in Lebanon, highlighting the critical role students played in mobilizing against corruption and economic mismanagement. By exploring the Lebanese case, the article also highlights how student activism has shaped political resistance, particularly in urban and peri-urban spaces that have been underexplored in the literature. This entry is drawn from the [Lebanon Unsettled Project](#) that invited Lebanese students to reflect on the 2019 uprisings and its aftermath.

The October 2019 Uprising in Lebanon as an Urbanized Revolt

Political scientists have long studied contentious politics and social movements. Since the Arab uprisings in 2011, the study of protest has emerged as a significant sub-field within Middle East Political Science. This work has enriched the broader scholarship on topics such as the political role of routine protests and “non-events,” the influence of religion, ethnic identity and social media, and the implications of protest outcomes beyond imme-

diated success and failure (for a comprehensive overview see, Allam et al. 2022). My personal contribution to this scholarship, through the co-edited volume *Beyond the Square: Urbanism and the Arab Uprisings*, expands the spatial perspective from public squares to the broader urban contexts where these uprisings occur. As with many uprisings across the Arab region, urbanization has profoundly influenced the frequency, spatial distribution, content and outcomes of uprisings worldwide. The Arab region has witnessed both rapid urbanization and unprecedented social upheaval, yet the link between these phenomena remains underexplored by scholars. The importance of Tahrir Square in Egypt and other metropolitan public squares during the Arab uprisings spurred only a minor, but significant, literature on the role of public space to protest.

The significance of considering spaces beyond the square in moments of protest was powerfully articulated once again in the October 2019 protest in Lebanon. I argue that this revolt marked Lebanon’s first fully urbanized uprising. The October 2019 protests were unprecedented in its geographic scale, three-month duration and the sheer number of protesters. Many scholars and activists describe the revolt as being geographically decentralized. Prior to October 2019, protest

in contemporary Lebanon has been largely city-based – and more precisely Beirut-based and centric – events. Nejme Square and Martyrs' Square in downtown Beirut near the seat of government power have long been the loci of revolt in the country. Although these metropolitan spaces continued to serve as the epicentre of the October 2019 protests, this movement also exhibited a remarkable (hierarchical) geographical diffusion.

In the north, protests erupted in Halba (Akkar) and Zgharta, Batroun and Lebanon's second largest city Tripoli, earning the moniker of 'Bride of the Revolution'. Smaller scale protests erupted in the town of Mount Lebanon – in the south, Saida and Nabatieh, and in the Bekka, Baalback and Zahle. In addition to unprecedented, synchronised protests erupting in these towns and cities alongside the capital, novel spaces of protest emerged that accentuated the fully urbanized nature of this revolt.

Role of Roadblocks in the 2019 Uprising

A key factor in the geographical diffusion of the protest was the use of roadblocks by protesters. Barricades, which involve the blocking of roads, have long been used as a tool of revolt. While Eric Hazan ([2013] 2015) argued that barricades had largely disappeared as a principal method of protest in the twentieth century, this tactic, along with other forms of spatial disruption, has seen a resurgence in the twenty first century. During the October 2019 uprising, barricades were set up with remarkable speed and geographical breadth. In an interview with the activist Nizar Hassan, he recalled that "by midnight on 17 October most vital highways and roads were blocked. In urban areas, even internal streets were blocked, usually by local working

-class men and women burning dumpsters... in the middle of the streets." Protesters moved quickly to block not only the streets and main traffic arteries in and around Beirut but also, through spontaneous uncoordinated – yet critically simultaneous – actions, to halt traffic on major roads across the country.

The blocking of the major highways ground the country to a halt, effectively creating an unofficial general strike. Sociologist Rima Majed argues that what made October 2019 a revolutionary moment was this unofficial mass strike (see also, Karam and Majed 2022). In the absence of labor movements that have been suppressed, defeated, and co-opted by the postwar ruling class, road closures became a means to undertake a mass strike. Notably, the linear barricade itself did not become a focal point for protesters. Instead, large crowds gathered in the centre of highways, transforming spaces typically reserved for cars into public areas for pedestrians. In Beirut, the Ring Bridge – part of Beirut's major ring road – quickly became a central site in the uprisings. This urban space, usually dominated by vehicles, was transformed by student-led demonstrators who reimagined this area as an outdoor apartment – adding their sofas, fridges and chairs. An online advert was even posted on the website Airbnb offering the opportunity to book a night in what was commonly known as the apartment of the people.

Similar practices occurred in highways throughout the country. Most notably along the highways in Jel el-Dib and Zouq but also main roads in and out of major urban centres such as Tripoli, Batroun and Byblos. A local autonomy was established through the national practice of blocking highways in which not only demands were made but prevailing cultural values challenged, spatial

forms transformed and new social meanings for urban space explored. As one participant in the revolt on the highway in Jel el-Dib described,

The revolt made us see our city in a different way...who would have expected us to be laughing, crying, screaming in the middle of the highway, no one. This is what made it very special because we were appropriating the spaces and being ourselves for a short period of time.

The highway was not only blocked but its function was transformed from a space of mobility to a place of public revolt, play and debate.

The October 2019 Uprising as a Revolt against Neoliberal Urbanization

Several scholars have argued that the October 2019 revolt was a reaction against the neoliberal system that was established by Rafi Hariri following the end of the Civil War. Hariri's neoliberal project resulted in the production of a particular urban state space in Lebanon. It solidified Beirut as the political and economic hub of the country, prioritizing investments in real estate and large-scale urban construction projects as the primary drivers of economic growth, often at the expense of industry, manufacturing and agriculture. The result was the rapid urbanisation of the country, nearly 90 percent of the population now live in urban areas. As a result, rural ways of living and spaces have largely been absorbed into larger urban units. This extended urbanization has intensified the importance of collective consumption through urban services, a dynamic observed globally by scholars like Manuel Castells (1983) and Henri Lefebvre (1996). However, the provision of public

goods, though essential, is often unprofitable for private capital, making urban issues a central focus of political conflict.

While a WhatsApp tax may have been the spark for the protest, the demonstrators made clear that this was a revolt against the entire political class and the collapse in basic living standards. In the October 2019 uprisings, protesters focused many of the demands on specifically urban issues. The uprising was notably both city-based and related to the entire urban fabric, including public services, real estate, the provision of urban goods and services (such as electricity, water and transport) and access to urban (public) space. Lebanese youth, and students in particular, played a central role in both leading many of the actions, like blocking roads and creating encampments, and in shaping the demands of the protest. The uprising brought together Lebanese youth in a manner and scale that had not been witnessed before. Several student groups abandoned traditional political parties and independent student groups grew and new spaces of movement-building were created (Chehayeb and Majzoub 2021).

Like other regions worldwide, Lebanon's expanding young urban middle class has grown increasingly angered with corruption, repressive regimes, and the shrinking provision of public goods, sparking widespread protests. Urbanization has made the state more integral to people's everyday lives, especially through the provision of basic urban services. Subsequently, the absence of the state provisioned services is felt more acutely by the population. This frustration is encapsulated in the common lament: "Where is the state?"—not as a call for the existence of government, but as a critique of the absence of a functioning state in the context of its increasingly pervasive presence.

Conclusion

Urbanization continues to rapidly expand across the region and will continue to be a major structuring force of contentious politics throughout the Arab region. The October 2019 uprisings in Lebanon underscore the critical need for political science to deepen its exploration of the intersection between urbanization and contentious politics. The case of Lebanon demonstrates how urbanization has not only altered the landscape of protest but also intensified the public's reliance on – and subsequent discontent with – the state,

particularly when basic urban services fail. The transformation of highways – often led by students – into sites of public debate and revolt, the widespread diffusion of protest, and the profound reaction against neoliberal urbanization all point to the urgent need for scholars to examine how urbanization shapes, and is shaped by, political and student movements. Understanding this intersection will be crucial for addressing the future challenges that arise as urban centres continue to grow and as the demands of urban populations become increasingly central to political conflicts. ♦

Students making the performative map at Lebanon Unsettled project workshop at USEK in July 2022. Image provided by the author. [Click on the image to watch a video on the project.](#)*

* The Lebanon Unsettled project is an academic collaboration between the London School of Economics and the Holy Spirit University of Kaslik (USEK) in Lebanon. The initiative deepens the socio-spatial analyses of the 2019 protests by focusing on protests outside the central public spaces of the metropolis Beirut. The project seeks to highlight alternative voices, geographies and histories of this moment. After significant delays due to a hostile host institution (USEK), COVID-19, Lebanon's economic collapse and the Beirut port explosion, a workshop with USEK students was finally held in July 2022. During the week-long workshop, participants engaged in both individual and collective performative mappings of the revolt. These mappings explored key socio-spatial elements of the protest, such as the transformation of the highways into space of leisure and play, the frequent use of terms like *harj wa marej* (uproar) and iconic images of the revolt like “the fist” and the Dunkin’ Donuts and Sea Sweet stores that becomes symbols of the movement.

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